

Crystallization of alumina in aluminosilicate matrix

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Alkaline aluminate has been synthesized at a desired mole ratio of Al_2O_3 : SiO_2 through a non-conventional route. $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ is the source material for generating α - Al_2O_3 to be dispersed in the glassy phase. The overall composition contains about 80% Al_2O_3 . Glass may dissolve some amount of Al_2O_3 . In these compositions alkaline earth oxides such as MgO and CaO act very well as dopant for controlling the grain size of Al_2O_3 as well as viscosity of the glassy phase.

Most of the alumina bearing bodies are fabricated from naturally occurring high alumina materials where the system always contains some low melting glasses from the impurities. Even in the other system crystal growth cannot be controlled. In the present method growth can be tailor-made by changing the exchangeable cation and the co-crystalline phase is of refractory nature. The generation of corundum phase alongwith mullite under varying conditions have been done by many scientists¹. Nitodas and Sotirchos² carried out comprehensive study on the chemical vapour co-deposition of silica, alumina and aluminosilicates from SiCl_4 - AlCl_3 - H_2O - CO_2 mixtures. Temuujin *et al.*³ investigated the mechanochemical formation and homogeneity of aluminosilicate precursors with respect to influence of particle size and chemical form of the aluminium hydroxide starting material.

The present investigation was undertaken to compose an alumina bearing body through a nonconventional route. The alkaline earth aluminosilicate was synthesized at a desired mole ratio of Al_2O_3 : SiO_2 . The material was very much active and at higher temperature it offered a liquid phase. It was interacted with Al_2O_3 added in the form of hydroxide. The alkaline earth oxide such as MgO and CaO acted as dopants for controlling the grain size of Al_2O_3 . The basis of selection of CaO and MgO as dopant is that alkaline earth cations usually act as a growth suppressor, which is the essential condition for good sintering for Al_2O_3 and moreover MgO forms a spinel phase which offers strength in the grain boundary.

Results and discussion

The synthetic aluminosilicate hydrogel having empiri-

cal formula $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{SiO}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ had molar ratio of Al_2O_3 : SiO_2 as 1 : 3, bulk density 0.485 g/cm^3 and CEC 3.25 meq/g . The synthetic exchanger possessed high CEC compared to other inorganic exchangers and the conversion into Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} form was more or less complete as tested by CEC measurement. The reactivity of Al_2O_3 with aluminosilicate glassy phase depends on the sequence of the thermal changes and the viscosity of the glassy phase. Loss of zeolitic water along with dehydroxylation of all hydroxide merged in both the cases to a broad peak at 220° (endo). A distinct exothermic peak was observed at 1120° with CaO substituted exchanger, which might be related to some crystallization reaction as assisted by CaO (figures not shown). It is to be noted here that the mineralizer, i.e. CaO and MgO were added in the reaction mixture in the form of exchanging cation where the distribution was more homogeneous compared to the mechanical mixture of the system. In case of mechanical mixture, there is every possibility of intense dopant interaction in certain spots due to some possible inhomogeneity and the reaction rate cannot be controlled. In case of dopant in the exchangeable position, the reaction rate was controlled by the slower release of the dopant. The distribution of the dopant was more homogeneous which is very much needed for this type of glass ceramic bodies. MgO did not show any such peak indicating delayed crystallization rate.

During sintering shrinkage occurred due to removal of residual water from the system, particle migration at the initial stage. This was exhibited in the shrinkage temperature curve upto 1300° , followed by the rapid shrinkage rate due to glass formation and crystallization. The magnitude of shrinkage was higher which might be related to grain growth.

The magnitude of apparent porosity of the fired body is an indicative of the sintering process either in the presence and absence of liquid phase. The results are in good conformity with the shrinkage data. Upto 1350° the rate of porosity reduction was slow followed by a rapid rate, which might be due to formation of glass and its subsequent flow in the formed pores. The minimum porosity achieved was 3% with CaO substituted composition. The viscosity of the glassy phase was the contributory factor for difference in porosity in these two systems.

True density of a mixed phase system is always related to the development of different crystalline phases as well as the amount and nature of the glassy phase. The nature of the true density curves (Fig. 1) was identical in both the systems and the inflection at 1400° indicated the secondary crystallization of Al_2O_3 . Due to high viscosity of MgO bearing glass, the crystallization rate was comparatively slow.

Fig. 1. True density vs sintering temperature curves of samples fired at different temperatures.

For identification of the generated crystalline phase during firing, X-ray diffraction patterns were taken for the samples fired at 1350, 1400 and 1450°. The major crystalline phase identified was corundum.

The assessment of the microstructure, i.e. the relative grain development, their distribution, nature of the pores was made from the micrographs obtained from scanning electron microscopy. SiO_2 has a low stability in Al_2O_3 and segregated to grain boundaries. When enough SiO_2 is present a liquid phase, formed at high temperatures, which on cooling forms a glass and crystallization occurs depending on composition. Here Al_2O_3 crystallized mostly in equiaxed form with sharp grain boundaries at 1300°. The grain growth in this system was mainly due to the presence of glass and

the alkaline earth dopants. In case of MgO growth was low. The local concentrations of the dopants have a strong effect on the microstructural evolution. But in the present investigation, the dopant distribution was more homogeneous and they were released from the ion exchange sites. MgO addition led to an equiaxed microstructure with a narrow distribution of dihedral angles, suggesting that all grain boundary energies are equal and that of MgO reduced the anisotropy of alumina.

It is suggested that MgO changed the wetting behavior of the silicate liquid in aluminate, MgO increased the solubility of SiO_2 in Al_2O_3 leading to a reduction in the SiO_2 content at the grain boundaries compared to CaO. In case of CaO the glass distribution was inhomogeneous throughout the microstructure. Thus in this system, densification occurred in presence of liquid phase and the extra liquid made the process rapid. Due to the presence of highly viscous glass the other phases might not grow enough to be resolved in the microstructure.

Experimental

Synthesis of the aluminosilicate hydrogel and conversion into Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} form were performed by the wet interaction of alkali silicate and aluminate solutions². The processed dry powder was converted to Ca and Mg forms by the process of ion exchange in batchwise system. The extra alumina was added in the form of hydroxide and milled properly for homogenization. For preparation of the compacts, the mixture was calcined at 900° to remove gel water and the dry powder was fabricated into pellets and bars in a hydraulic press at a pressure of 1500 kg/cm². No extra binder was used. 10% uncalcined powder was used as a green bond.

The properties of the sintered product were examined by following the standard methods⁴. X-Ray diffraction patterns were taken using a Philips PW 1710 diffractometer. SEM analysis was performed on a Hitachi-S530A microscope.

References

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